

Counsellors' Participation in In-Service Training Programmes For Quality Assurance in Counselling Services in Secondary Schools in Anambra State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined counsellors' participation in in-service training programmes for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State. Three research questions guided the study. The descriptive survey research design was employed in the study. Population of the study constituted all the 259 counsellors within 259 secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample of the study constituted 155 counsellors drawn from the entire population of counsellors from 155 secondary schools in Anambra State selected at 60% (percent) using the stratified random sampling technique. A questionnaire personally constructed by the researchers, which had 21-items and titled: "Counsellors' Participation in In-Service Training Programmes for Quality Assurance in Counselling Services Questionnaire (CPISTPQACSQ)" was the instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was validated by three experts from Guidance and Counselling Department and Measurement and Evaluation Department. Reliability of the instrument was established through a pilot by sampling 15 counsellors from secondary schools in Enugu State and data collected were measured using Cronbach Alpha statistical method which yielded an internal consistency reliability value of 0.79, showing that the instrument was reliable. Data were analyzed using simple percentages and mean scores. Findings of the study indicated that the percentage of counsellors' that participated in in-service training programmes for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State was minimal and low. Their participation in on-the-job and off-the-job in-service training programmes was low as well indicating that the counsellors did not show much participation in these training programmes investigated. Based on the findings of this study recommendations were made and among them include that the State Government in collaboration with the Anambra State Post Primary Schools Service Commission (PPSSC) should support counsellors' active participation in in-service training programmes through adequate funding, bursary, sponsorship and scholarship.

Key words: *Counsellors, In-Service training, Quality assurance, Counselling services, Secondary schools*

Introduction

There is doubt whatsoever that Counsellors are one of the important personnel in the Nigerian secondary school system that are charged with the responsibility of advising and guiding students' to work towards the right path of building good personalities for themselves. Through counselling services provided in the secondary schools, students' would find solutions to solve their educational or academic, career or vocational, personal and social problems so as to leave a sound and fulfilled life in the society. Counselling is therefore one of the guidance service which leads to the process of learning in which individuals learn about themselves, that helps them to achieve self-direction or development (Osakwe, 2007). Osakwe further identifying the importance of counsellors in the secondary schools attested that guidance counsellors have become more necessary for post-primary school candidates and primary school leavers who will have access to secondary education. Notably, many important problems would arise which will require that the students need the assistance of guidance counsellors. Shertzer and Stones cited in Osakwe (2007) observed the major activities of counsellors in secondary school as the provision of a helping relationship to students, which will enable them to examine and cope with their developmental concern. With the assistance of counsellors in the secondary education system, the country will produce youths that are occupationally competent, psychologically well adjusted, morally healthy and capable of making sound decisions in life.

A counsellor, according to Osakwe (2007), is a guidance specialist who is technically trained and experienced, ready to assist, to develop skills of solving students' problems. Oguzie, Oguzie, Nnadi, Mokwelu and Obi (2019) viewed counsellors as professionally trained personnel who render helping services to clients with the aim of increasing clients' understanding of their 'self' and the 'environment' so as to adjust properly and be productive members of the society. However, the secondary education has been set up with some goals which has been highlighted by the Federal Republic of Nigeria in the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013) as providing trained manpower in applied, technological and commerce at sub-professional grades; providing entrepreneurial, technical and vocational job specific skills for self-reliance and for agricultural, industrial, commercial and economic development; inspiring students with a desire for self-improvement and achievement of excellence; fostering patriotism, national unity and security education with emphasis on the common ties in spite of our diversity; and raising morally upright and well-adjusted individuals who can think independently and rationally, respect the views and feeling of others and appreciate the dignity of labour, among others. All the above secondary education goals cannot be effectively achieved without the efforts and contributions of quality counsellors who will render effective services for quality assurance (QA) in guidance and counselling services in the secondary school. According to Aigboje (2007), Quality assurance (QA) is basically how good a product is in order to deliver and achieve positive results. It entails that a product meets a given standard during the process of manufacturing so as to meet the customers' satisfaction. Describing quality assurance (QA) within the context of the present study, Agu (2014) sees (QA) the effectiveness with which the educational system promotes or reinforces among children and young people, the culture and values, morals and attitude

particular to a given society. In the context of this study, quality assurance is taken to mean the process of ensuring desired level of quality in a product or service by paying adequate attention to all activities involved from the production of such products or services to their delivery.

Quality assurance cannot be achieved outside the major variables that affect quality education, in which counsellors are one of them. Agu (2014) further opined that the effectiveness and actualization of educational objectives rests in the hands of the teachers including counsellors who greatly determines the quality of education provided in every society. Counsellors just like the teachers need continuous training and retraining for their effectiveness in service delivery. Wokocha (2014) maintained that indubitable teacher quality has been one of important key to improving students learning achievements and researches have shown that students of effective teachers showed impressive gains better than those with ineffective teachers. In the same vein, secondary schools with quality counsellors who render effective services will positively impacts more on students' academic achievements, than schools without effective counsellors and counselling services. To ensure counsellors quality for effective curricular delivery, then, their continuous in-service training should be emphasized and sustained.

Ezugoh (2017) opined that many scholars agree that organizations that train their employees consistently have better outcomes than those that do not. When business environments change quickly and abruptly, it is typically the organizations with the best trained employees that adapt and adjust most efficiently. Therefore, one way of assuring quality counsellors for quality guidance and counselling services in the secondary school in Nigeria including Anambra State is through in-service programmes which ensure that counsellors constantly update their knowledge and competences in order to render effective services for achievement of educational goals and objectives. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) indicated the importance of in-service training programmes for quality assurance of counselling services by stressing that under section 5, pg.44 and 45 of the National Policy on Education that in-service training shall be an integral part of continuing teacher education which is mandatory that all school proprietors provide in-service education for teachers. Efforts towards improvement of quality education at all level shall also include improvement and regulation of career-long professional development of teachers through the provision of a wide range of programmes and multiple pathways to provide serving teachers with regular opportunities for updating their knowledge and skills. The benefits of in-service training provided for teachers or counsellors can never be overemphasized, as this will assist to develop capacity building of the personnel (like the school counsellors) by keeping them abreast of latest teaching or counselling techniques for the various categories of students in the school. As regards, Government shall continue to make provision for the training of teachers in guidance and counselling (FRN, 2013, p.59). In-service training programmes in essence are efforts made by any institution to boost competences of their employees and where the required teachers are not available; efforts have been made for training and retraining of workers. No matter how automated an organization may be, high productivity depends on the level of the effectiveness of the workforce. Every organization in the school must have good training programmes that will provide the employee information on professional opportunities for self-improvement and development to meet the

challenges and requirements of new equipment and new techniques of performing a task (Udeozor cited in Ezugoh, 2017). Wokocha (2014) describes in-service training programmes as the systematic maintenance, improvement and broadening of knowledge, skills, and development of personal qualities necessary for the execution of professional member's working life. Counsellors' in-service training programmes therefore as described in the present study entails all on-the-job or off-the-job training and retraining programmes provided or organized for counsellors to boost their skills, competences, quality, efficiency and effectiveness in order to render quality counselling services for achievement of educational goals and objectives.

Example of these in-service training programmes includes on-the-job and off-the-job in-service training programmes like induction, orientation, mentoring, apprenticeship, coaching, conferences, workshops, university education, job rotation, among others (Ezugoh, 2017; Wokocha, 2014; Zamumuzi 2004). Therefore, in-service training programmes as observed by Lai-Yeung (2014) can be provided for counsellors in the secondary schools inform of seminars, workshops, conferences, coaching, among others, on areas that will develop counsellors roles and communication skills, interpersonal skills with clients, counselling skills (questioning skills), knowledge related to guidance and counselling (therapy theories), ways to deal with own issues relating to time management, emotional intelligence, knowledge about practical issues, cases studies/skills in handling cases and collaborative skills with stakeholders. Counsellors' regular and constant participation in in-service training programmes cannot be overemphasized because this seems to be beneficial to them. In-service training programmes enables counsellors to update their knowledge and skills in modern means of counselling services. According to Beecroft (2019), in-service training programmes enables counsellors to familiarize themselves with basic principles of the solution oriented approach; to get new tools for the counseling work; to enhance the importance of cooperation between guidance counsellors and other teaching staff; to offer tools for multi-professional cooperation - guidance counsellor as a part of multi-professional teams; and to increase information on the transition phase from the compulsory education to secondary education. Several studies conducted by different scholars like (Beecroft, 2019; Ezugoh, 2017; Osakwe, 2007) among others found that in-service training programmes are beneficial to recipients. Şahbaz (2011) conducted a study and found that in-service training programmes are of benefits for teachers in handling students' with disabilities, although, the programmes were not effectively organized for teachers in schools. Mbongo, Möwes and Chata (2016) asserted that teacher counsellors viewed inadequate training as one of the key factors impacting the successful implementation of school guidance and counselling.

A look at the secondary school in Anambra State, it seems as if the counsellors are not in existence, they remain ineffective in counselling students in schools because too much focus is on academics leaving out counselling services in the school. The development of skills and other necessary competences that are required for achieving the objectives of secondary education of technological and entrepreneurship development in the society cannot be guaranteed unless quality assurance of guidance counselling services is channeled towards this noble objective. Amidst recent reports from various states and national level call for educational reform initiatives to raise academic standards, add course requirements, require competency testing, and otherwise

upgrade the quality of the secondary schools but very little attention has been given to the need for improving guidance and counselling services through counsellors' in-service training and retraining (Osakwe, 2007).

Consequently, effective learning can take place only within a supportive environment of which quality counselling services is a crucial component. When students have problems, they turn to those whom they know best, and who they think can help them most. Surveys have shown that the adults to whom students of all ages are most likely to turn to, after their parents, are teachers. Most schools are far from having enough quality school counsellors or other specialists to provide a comprehensive quality guidance counselling programme for students' development. As it is, counsellors' hands are normally full as a result of dealing with high risk students who have special needs or emotional problems, and most other students are lucky if they can gain access to a counsellor more than a few times during a school year. Yet all students, especially at the secondary school level, need the support of a quality counsellor who is a friendly adult that cares about them personally; someone who they can confide in, who can help them deal with the challenges of growing up, keeping up with their studies, and planning their careers. Counsellors can only be effective in schools in Anambra State when they regularly participate in training and retraining counselling programmes that will keep them abreast on the modern counselling strategies. It is against this background that this study examined counsellors' participation in in-service training programmes for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

Counsellors are one of the important human machineries in secondary schools in Anambra State. They assist and guide students' through their learning process to overcome difficulties in their academics. Given the important roles and responsibilities of counsellors in the secondary schools in Anambra State as regards to their contributions towards the personal, social and academic development of students and assist them to make realistic career choices and decisions; yet counsellors' quality assurance is something that is still questionable. This is owing to the fact that there have been a lot of reported cases concerning secondary school students' maladjustments and deviant behaviour. If counsellors were to be very effective in their counselling services, lots of students' indecent acts and ill-behaviour would have been curtailed and controlled. The ugly situation of secondary school students' indiscipline and immoral acts has left a lot of doubts in the minds of education stakeholders including the researcher concerning the quality of counsellors and counselling services in the school. With the recent happenings in the society, counsellors' in-service training must be stressed out in order to help student to leave a fulfilled life without damaging their future.

The inadequacies in utilizing quality in-service training programmes in secondary schools seem to have negative effect on students' academics. The researcher has in addition noticed the existence of poor study habits, substance abuse, high increase in examination malpractices and difficulty in coping with examination anxiety among adolescent learners, hence the importance of counsellors in-service training programmes for quality assurance in counselling services in the

present study. The introduction of guidance and counselling services in Anambra State secondary schools has mandated the school authorities to support counsellors' in-service training for (QA) in counselling services in schools. This study therefore, sought to determine counsellors' participation in in-service training programmes for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State, which is equally the problem of the study.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine counsellors' participation in in-service training programmes for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the objectives of the study aimed at discovering:

1. The frequency percentage of counsellors' participation in in-service training programmes for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Types of on-the-job in-service training programmes in which the counsellors' participate for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Types of off-the-job in-service training programmes in which the counsellors' participate for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following three research questions were raised in order to conduct the study:

1. What is percentage of counsellors' participation in in-service training programmes for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What are the types of on-the-job in-service training programmes in which the counsellors' participate for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State?
3. What are the types of off-the-job in-service training programmes in which the counsellors' participate for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Method

The descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study. This design was used to collect data from a sample of counsellors in order to share their opinions concerning their participation in in-service training programmes for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State. Thereafter, from the results of the findings generalization and conclusion will be drawn. According to Akilaiya, Opute-Imala and Ezoem (2002) and Nworgu (2015), the descriptive survey design is used in observing what is happening to sample subjects or variables in order to generate necessary primary data for any study. Population of the study constituted all the 259 counsellors within 259 secondary schools in Anambra State. Information concerning the counsellors in the State public secondary schools was obtained from the Planning, Research and Statistics Department, Anambra State Post Primary Schools Service Commission as at March, 2019.

The sample of this study constituted 155 counsellors drawn from the entire population of counsellors from 155 secondary schools in Anambra State selected at 60% (percent) using the stratified random sampling technique. To do the selection, the entire 259 public secondary schools

and their counsellors in Anambra State were first stratified and placed according to stratum in their six (6) education zones and selection was now randomly made. Sixty percent (60%) of the counsellors in the public secondary schools were sampled from each of the six education zones in Anambra State. This gave rise to a sample size of 155 counsellors selected for sampling in the study. Justification for using 60% was a means to enable the researchers have control over a large sizeable number of samples, that is, counsellors in the state public secondary schools from the large population of counsellors and schools existing within the six education zones in Anambra State. The choice of 60% (for a large number) is also in line with the recommendation of Nworgu (2015) who identified that 10% to 80% of any given population is adequate for any research work. A questionnaire personally constructed by the researchers, which had 21-items and titled: "Counsellors' Participation in In-Service Training Programmes for Quality Assurance in Counselling Services Questionnaire (CPISTPQACSQ)" was the instrument for data collection. Construction of the questionnaire was guided by the purpose of the study and research questions. The items were organized in two clusters and structured on a 4-point scale weighted as follows: Strongly Agree (SA) - 4, Agree (A) - 3, Disagree (D) - 2, Strongly Disagree (SD) - 1 in order to answer the research questions. The questionnaire was validated by three experts from Guidance and Counselling Department and Measurement and Evaluation Department. The experts determined the face and content validity of the questionnaire in terms of items clarity, language and sentence construction. Corrections were made on few items which were equally incorporated before the final printing of the questionnaire for distribution. Reliability of the instrument was established through a pilot by sampling 15 counsellors from secondary schools in Enugu State and data collected were measured using Cronbach Alpha statistical method which yielded an internal consistency reliability value of 0.79, showing that the instrument was reliable. The questionnaire was distributed to the respondents on a face to face, direct contact with the researchers. An on-the-spot method was also adopted by the researchers in distributing copies of the questionnaire to ensure maximum recovery of the questionnaire administered. Copies of the questionnaire for the counsellors were administered to them by the researchers with the help of two research assistants. These research assistants were trained on how to administer the questionnaire to the respondents. The exercise of distributing copies of the questionnaire took a period of three weeks of completion. This enabled both the researchers and the research assistants to get the respondents at their different locations and likewise wait for them to fill the questionnaire right there on the spot. A total of 155 copies of questionnaires were printed and distributed. All copies of the questionnaire distributed to the respondents were retrieved and recovered back by the researchers and research assistants. Thus the rate of return was 100%. Data were analyzed using simple percentages and mean scores.

The frequency distribution and percentages were used to analyze data and answer research question 1; while the scores were used to answer research question 2 and 3. The decision rule for the research questions was based on the mean scale, which was benchmarked on 2.50. Only mean scores of the respondents' statements which rated 2.50 and above were taken as an indication of Strongly Agree and Agree, and therefore, accepted. While mean scores of the

respondents' statements which rated below 2.50 was regarded as an indication of Disagree and Strongly Disagree and therefore not accepted.

Results

Table 1: Frequency and percentage scores of counsellors' concerning their participation in in-service training programmes for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State

N= 155

S/N	Please show your agreement concerning participation in-service training programmes:	Frequency	Percentages (%)
1	Weekly participation	0	0
2	Monthly participation	4	2.3
3	Twice a month participation	2	1.3
4	Yearly participation	58	37.4
5	Quarterly participation	18	11.6
6	Five times above yearly participation	6	3.9
7	None at all	67	43.2
Total		155	100%

Result analysis in Table 1 revealed the frequency participation of the counsellors' in in-service training programmes for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State. The result showed that there was no weekly participation by the counsellors in in-service training programmes, 4 of the counsellors representing 2.3% agreed to their monthly participation in in-service training programmes, while 2 of the counsellors representing 1.3% agreed to twice a month participation in in-service training programmes. Others include that 58 (that is, 37.4%) agreed to their yearly participation in in-service training programmes, while 18 of the counsellors (that is, 11.6%) agreed to their quarterly participation in in-service training programmes. 6 of the counsellors representing 3.9% agreed to five times above yearly participation in in-service training programmes. However, 67 of the counsellors representing 43.2% agreed to none at all participation to in-service training programmes. This result indicated that the counsellors' participation in in-service training programmes was low and minimal for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 2: Mean scores ratings of counsellors' concerning types of on-the-job in-service training programmes in which the counsellors' participate for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State

N= 155

S/N	Please show your agreement concerning your participation in the following on-the-job in-service training programmes:	SA	A	D	SD	Mean Score	Decision
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8	Orientation/Induction training programmes for newly employed counselors	25	33	53	44	2.25	Disagree
9	Seminars organized by the principals for counsellors in the school through guest talk	17	27	61	50	2.07	Disagree
10	Job rotation in the school for counsellors	34	54	28	39	2.54	Agree
11	Mentoring of newly employed counsellors by the old experienced ones	19	43	37	56	2.16	Disagree
12	Workshops organized for counsellors by the school authorities	37	24	53	41	2.37	Disagree
13	Guidance for task performance by a colleague on the job	38	44	33	40	2.52	Agree
14	Training through observation by a superior (observer)	14	31	60	50	2.06	Disagree
Grand Mean score						2.28	Disagree

Result analysis in Table 2 revealed counsellors' participation in on-the-job in-service training programmes for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State. The result showed that only items 10 and 13 of the counsellors' responses rated above the acceptable mean score of 2.50, showing their agreement with these two statements. All other items 8, 9, 11, 12 and 14 rated below the acceptable mean score of 2.50, showing their disagreement with the statements. The grand mean of 2.28 indicated that the counsellors reacted negatively to majority of the statements in order to show that their participation in on-the-job in-service training programmes was low and minimal. The result indicated that the counsellors did not participate much in on-the-job training programmes for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 3: Mean scores ratings of counsellors' concerning types of off-the-job in-service training programmes in which the counsellors' participate for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State

N= 155

S/N	Please show your agreement concerning your participation in the following off-the-job in-service training programmes:	SA	A	D	SD	Mean Score	Decision
15	Continuing University education training courses for counsellors in award of higher degree	59	68	15	13	3.12	Agree
16	Computer-based training organized outside the school for counselors	13	28	63	51	2.02	Disagree
17	Participation in conferences organized by the Association of Counselling	22	32	53	48	2.18	Disagree
18	Participation in conferences organized in the university for counsellors	14	35	50	56	2.05	Disagree

19	Workshops for counsellors outside the school premises	17	47	51	40	2.26	Disagree
20	Coaching by an expert away from the school	28	38	61	28	2.43	Disagree
21	Apprenticeship or internship programmes for counsellors	21	33	57	44	2.20	Disagree
Grand Mean score						2.32	Disagree

Result analysis in Table 3 revealed counsellors' participation in off-the-job in-service training programmes for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State. The result showed that only item 15 of the counsellors' responses rated above the acceptable mean score of 2.50, showing their agreement with the statement. All other items 16, 17, 18, 19, 20 and 20 rated below the acceptable mean score of 2.50, showing their disagreement with the statements. The grand mean of 2.28 indicated that the counsellors reacted negatively to majority of the statements in order to show that their participation in off-the-job in-service training programmes was low and minimal. The result indicated that the counsellors did not participate much in off-the-job training programmes for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion of Findings

Finding of the study revealed that the percentage of counsellors' who participated in in-service training programmes was low and minimal. This finding indicated that none of the counsellors participated weekly in in-service training programmes, 2.3% of the counsellors participated monthly in in-service training programmes, 1.3% of the counsellors participated twice a month in in-service training programmes, 37.4% of the counsellors only participated yearly in in-service training programmes and 11.6% of the counsellors participated quarterly in in-service training programmes. Furthermore, 3.9% participated more than five times above yearly in in-service training programmes and 43.2% of the counsellors did not participate in in-service training programmes. The above finding showed that a great number of the counsellors did not participate at all in in-service training programmes. Quite a small number participated only once yearly in in-service training programme. Counsellors' low participation in in-service training programmes shows their ineffectiveness in counselling services creating difficulties for quality to be assured in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State. This finding agrees with Şahbaz (2011) who found that counselling programmes were not effectively organized for teachers in schools in which their lack of exposure to constant in-service training was also a challenge. The finding does not corroborate with the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) directives in the national policy on education who confirmed that constant in-service training programmes should be organized for counsellors by school proprietors. With a large number or portion of counsellors' poor participation in in-service training programmes in the secondary schools this would have negative effect on quality assurance of counselling services.

It was also discovered through one of the findings that the counsellors did not participate much in on-the-job training programmes for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State. Their participation in on-the-job in-service training programmes was low and minimal. The finding further revealed that there were low

participation of counsellors in orientation/induction training programmes, seminars organized by the principals for counsellors in school through guest talk, mentoring of newly employed counsellors by the old experienced ones, workshops organized by the school authorities and training through observation. Job rotation and guidance were the areas in which the counsellors showcased high participation. This finding corroborates with Ezugoh (2017) who found that on-the-job training in-service training programmes were not appropriately provided for educators for their improved productivity in adult literacy centres in Delta State. Such on-the-job in-service training as induction training and orientation, mentoring, are not provided for educators. Given the above finding of the present study, it can be deduced that counsellors' poor participation in on-the-job in-service training programmes has negative effective on quality assurance of counselling services in secondary schools. Since secondary schools have been set up with certain objectives, students need quality counselling services so as to enable them fulfill their dreams and also work towards the achievement of the objectives of secondary schools. Osakwe (2007) confirmed that the development of skills and other necessary competences that are required for achieving the objectives of secondary education of technological and entrepreneurship development in the society cannot be guaranteed unless quality assurance of guidance counselling services is channeled towards this noble objective, thus the need for counsellors' in-service training and retraining.

The finding of this study also revealed that the counsellors did not participate much in off-the-job training programmes for quality assurance in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State. Their participation in off-the-job in-service training programmes was low and minimal. This finding included that there were low participation of counsellors in the following off-the-job in-service training programmes as computer-based training programmes organized outside the school, conferences organized by the Counselling Association, conferences organized in the university for counsellors, outside workshops, coaching by an expert and apprenticeship or internship programmes for counsellors. The counsellors only showed great participation in continuing university education training courses that led to award of a higher degree. Whereby, counsellors' do not participate in off-the-job in-service training programmes, this will have negative consequences on quality assurance of counselling services in the schools causing lots of difficulties in attainment of educational goals. This finding although work against the directives of the FRN but still corroborates with Ezugoh (2017) who found that opportunities for off-the-job training through tertiary education which enabled educators improve their competence in their teaching area, free educational scholarships provided as means of improving educators level of competences and skill upgrading, long and short courses abroad, long and short courses within Nigeria in order to improve educators work efficiency and computer-based training were not provided for educators in order to provide them the necessary information to function actively in the literacy centres. Lai-Yeung (2014) and Mbongo, Möwes and Chata (2016) confirmed that teacher counsellors viewed inadequate training as one of the key factors impacting the successful implementation of school guidance and counselling. All the findings of this study show that priority interest and adequate attention needs to be focused on counsellors' in-service

training programmes for quality assurance to be properly harnessed in counselling services in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Conclusion

The services of counsellors are of utmost importance in the secondary schools in Anambra State because they assist in ensuring that students learn under a peaceful and conducive atmosphere in the schools. Counsellors' provide answers and solutions not only to students' learning difficulties but also to their vocational and personal-social problems. Given the important roles of counsellors in attaining quality assurance in counselling services in the secondary schools, their constant in-service training which comes as on-the-job or off-the-job training should not be overlooked. Constant participation of counsellors in in-service training programmes will improve their quality, thereby boosting their effectiveness for quality assurance in service delivery. However, the present study submits that the frequency to which counsellors' participate in on-the-job and off-the-job in-service training programmes in the secondary schools was minimal and low. This situation which negatively affected quality assurance of counselling services in the schools calls for adequate redress.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations have been made:

1. The State Government in collaboration with the Anambra State Post Primary Schools Service Commission (PPSSC) should support counsellors' active participation in in-service training programmes through adequate funding, bursary, sponsorship and scholarship.
2. Principals of secondary schools in Anambra State should support counsellors' on-the-job training programmes by organizing constant orientation/induction training programmes, seminars, mentorship, workshops and training through observations for the counsellors.
3. Anambra State Post Primary Schools Service Commission (PPSSC) in collaboration with the State Government should financially sponsor counsellors in certain off-the-job training programmes like computer-based training programmes, conferences organized by the Counselling Association, conferences organized in the university, outside workshops, coaching by an expert and apprenticeship or internship programmes for counsellors.

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